

CHLOROBERYLLATES

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From conductometric measurements it has been shown that four chloroberyllate ions, namely, $[\text{BeCl}_3]'$, $[\text{BeCl}_4]''$, $[\text{BeCl}_5]'''$ and $[\text{BeCl}_6]''''$ exist in solution.

In a previous communication (Purkayastha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 257) it has been shown that four fluoberyllate ions, namely $[\text{BeF}_3]$ etc. $[\text{BeF}_3]'$, $[\text{BeF}_4]''$, $[\text{BeF}_5]'''$ and $[\text{BeF}_6]''''$ exist in solution and from the facts stated therein, it has been argued that beryllium, analogous to its neighbours, aluminium and magnesium in the periodic table, may form hexa-co-ordinated ions as far as our observations with fluoro compounds are concerned. Several double salts of aluminium and magnesium chlorides with alkali chlorides are described, but not a single double salt of BeCl_2 with alkali chloride is known. The failure in the isolation of double salts with beryllium chloride does not, however, exclude the probability of the existence of chloroberyllate ions in solution. A search demonstrating the existence and composition of the chloroberyllate ions in solution from conductometric measurements forms the subject matter of the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium Chloride.—A solution of BeCl_2 was prepared by treating a saturated solution of beryllium sulphate with calculated amount of barium chloride. The barium sulphate was filtered off through a silica bed. The concentration of the solution was ascertained by estimating both beryllium and chlorine. Be was precipitated as hydroxide with ammonia and ignited to BeO . Chlorine was estimated volumetrically by Volhard's method. The ratio of Be to Cl was found to be 1 : 1.982.

Ammonium Chloride.—The stock solution was prepared with Merck's NH_4Cl of reagent quality. Ammonia was estimated by distillation with alkali and by absorbing the distillate in a standard acid and titrating back the excess acid. Chlorine was estimated volumetrically in the same way as was done in the previous case.

Beryllium sulphate ($\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was prepared by digesting Kahlbaum's beryllium carbonate in H_2SO_4 and crystallising the product. The crystals were dissolved in warm water. The solution was acidified with sulphuric acid and recrystallised. The crystals were washed three times with ice-cold water and finally with alcohol till free from acid.

The conductivity apparatus was fitted with thermoionic valve amplifiers and so the experimental error in determining resistance was brought within

0.1%. The mean of the three values of resistance was always taken. The thermostat was so adjusted that the temperature varied within 0.05° . The platinum electrode was deplatinised and re-coated with a thin deposit of spongy platinum. In consideration of the precautions that have been taken in every step, it is clear that the probable error due to all sources cannot exceed 0.2%.

The reciprocal of the observed resistance *i.e.*, conductance was sufficient to draw the curve. So the cell constant was not determined. The conductances of the constituents, namely beryllium chloride and ammonium chloride solutions, were measured in the way as tabulated below (Table I); and the divergence from the additivity rule has been plotted against composition.

TABLE I
Conductance measurements with BeCl_2 and NH_4Cl
Temp. = 32.2° .

1		2	3		4	5	6		7	8
$M/20. \text{BeCl}_2$ soln. (c.c.)	Water added (c.c.)	Conductance of (1) $\times 10^3 = C_1$	$M/20. \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ soln. (c.c.)	Water added (c.c.)	Conductance of (3) $\times 10^3 = C_2$	$C_1 + C_2 = C_3$	$M/20. \text{BeCl}_2$ soln. (c.c.)	$M/20. \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ soln (c.c.)	Conductance of (6) $\times 10^3 = C_4$	$(C_3 - C_4) \times 10$
5	95	2.726	95	5	27.35	30.076	5	95	29.94	1.360
10	90	5.137	90	10	26.39	31.527	10	90	30.82	7.070
13	87	6.579	87	13	25.37	31.949	13	87	31.17	7.790
15	85	7.449	85	15	24.90	32.349	15	85	31.33	10.19
20	80	9.863	80	20	23.61	33.473	20	80	32.21	12.63
21	79	10.27	79	21	23.21	33.48	21	79	32.51	9.70
22	78	10.80	78	22	23.05	33.86	22	78	32.62	12.30
25	75	12.21	75	25	22.19	34.40	25	75	32.96	14.40
26	74	12.52	74	26	21.85	34.37	26	74	33.01	13.60
27	73	13.14	73	27	21.54	34.68	27	73	33.22	14.60
30	70	14.45	70	30	20.81	35.26	30	70	33.68	15.80
33.35	66.65	15.67	66.65	33.35	19.78	35.45	33.35	66.65	33.68	17.70
40	60	18.75	60	40	17.89	36.64	40	60	35.05	15.90
45	55	20.83	55	45	16.51	37.34	45	55	35.99	13.50
50	50	23.10	50	50	15.13	38.23	50	50	36.39	18.40
60	40	27.13	40	60	12.20	39.33	60	40	37.75	15.80
80	20	34.95	20	80	6.256	41.206	80	20	40.30	9.060
95	5	40.93	5	95	1.020	42.55	95	5	42.24	3.100

Difference from the least divergence from the additivity rule in each case has been plotted against composition (Fig. 1, curve I).

DISCUSSION

The curve I (Fig. I) showing the divergence from the additivity rule in the conductometric measurements of BeCl_2 with NH_4Cl has four maxima, clearly demarcated by the corresponding minima. The compositions of the solutions at these maxima indicate the formations of $[\text{BeCl}_3]'$, $[\text{BeCl}_4]''$, $[\text{BeCl}_5]'''$ and $[\text{BeCl}_6]''''$ in solution. These observations clearly indicate that there are four

chloroberyllates, analogous in composition to the four fluoberyllates, already reported. A comparative study of the fall in conductivity due to complex formations reveals that chloroberyllato complexes are much more unstable than the corresponding fluoberyllates. The fact that chloro complexes are very unstable and that these are four in number make it difficult to select out physico-chemical methods for their study. However, attempts are being made to substantiate the conclusion derived from the conductivity measurements by other physico-chemical measurements.

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